

Means of Forming Speech Competence of International Economists in the Process of Studying a Foreign Language of Academic and Professional Communication

Соколовська Олена Миколаївна¹

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Annotation. The article addresses the problem of forming foreign language speech competence of future specialists in international economic relations within the framework of foreign language academic and professional communication. The relevance of the study is determined by intensified globalization, expanding international economic cooperation, and increased demands for professional communication skills of economists working in multicultural and multilingual contexts. Foreign language proficiency is viewed not merely as a tool for everyday interaction but primarily as an instrument of professional activity that enables effective participation in international economic, business, and academic communication.

The study is grounded in the analysis of contemporary scientific approaches to foreign language competence development, including communicative, competence-based, intercultural, and integrated learning models. Particular attention is given to the formation of foreign language speech competence through the integration of professional content and language learning, the use of authentic materials, extensive reading, audio-visual resources, and interactive teaching methods. The pedagogical potential of CLIL, problem-based learning, case studies, business games, presentations, and training exercises is substantiated in the context of teaching a foreign language of academic and professional communication to future international economists.

The conclusions emphasize that the effectiveness of professional training in higher education depends on the creation of appropriate organizational, methodological, technological, and psychological-pedagogical conditions for foreign language learning. The formation of foreign language speech competence enables future specialists to act effectively in professional situations, engage in international dialogue, and adapt to the dynamic demands of the global economic environment. Further research prospects involve developing and implementing a blended-learning-based model of foreign language competence formation.

Keywords: competence-based approach, foreign language training; professionally-oriented learning, professional communication, CLIL-technologies, authentic learning materials.

¹ кандидат філологічних наук, доцент, доцент кафедри міжнародних економічних відносин та іноземних мов Центральноукраїнського національного технічного університету, м. Кропивницький, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2368-4102>

Особливості формування мовленнєвої компетентності економістів-міжнародників у процесі вивчення іноземної мови академічної та професійної комунікації

Анотація. У статті досліджено проблему формування іншомовної мовленнєвої компетентності майбутніх економістів-міжнародників у процесі вивчення іноземної мови академічної та професійної комунікації у закладах вищої освіти. Актуальність теми зумовлена глобалізаційними процесами, інтеграцією України в міжнародний економічний простір та підвищенням вимог до професійної підготовки фахівців у сфері міжнародних економічних відносин. Проаналізовано теоретичні підходи до визначення іншомовної компетентності, обґрунтовано доцільність інтеграції мовної й фахової підготовки із застосуванням підходу CLIL, автентичних матеріалів, елементів перекладу та активних методів навчання. Визначено умови ефективного формування іншомовної мовленнєвої компетентності, що сприяє підвищенню готовності майбутніх фахівців до професійної діяльності в міжнародному середовищі.

Ключові слова: компетентнісний підхід, іншомовна підготовка, професійно-орієнтоване навчання, фахова комунікація, CLIL-технології, автентичні навчальні матеріали.

Introduction

In the contemporary context of the dynamic development of global society and the deepening integration of Ukraine into the international community, the importance of intercultural and professional communication in the field of international economic relations has increased significantly. The intensification of political, economic, and cultural interconnections between countries leads to the emergence of new requirements for the professional training of specialists, particularly with regard to the level of proficiency in a foreign language as a tool of academic and professional communication. The ability to interact effectively with representatives of different cultures constitutes an essential prerequisite for successful professional activity, as it facilitates a deeper understanding of the specifics of international markets, patterns of consumer behaviour, and ethical norms determined by cultural context. In this regard, the formation of foreign language speech competence among future international economists acquires particular relevance and is considered one of the key directions for improving the system of higher education in Ukraine.

The issue of preparing future international economists for foreign language communication within the framework of studying a foreign language of academic and professional communication has been widely addressed in scholarly research devoted to various aspects of the formation of specialists' communicative competence. In particular, the works of N. Halskova, I. Zymnia, M. Canale, M. Swain, and other scholars examine the content and structure of communicative competence, while the conceptual understanding of the essence of foreign language competence is presented in the studies of L. Nezhvedylova, O. Samoilova, V. Tenishchev, O. Usanova, D. Hymes, and others. Special attention is paid to the analysis of the structure of foreign language competence and the specifics of its formation, as reflected in the works of M. Canale, O. Klymenko, N. Kostenko, and other researchers. The problems of forming and developing foreign language competence among future economists have become the subject of scientific inquiry by L. Mykhailenko, I. Humenna, T. Koval, O. Zelikovska, S. Nikolaieva, O. Tarnopolskyi, N. Kostenko, and other scholars. Thus, L. Mykhailenko substantiates the position that foreign language competence is an integral component of the professional competence of a future specialist, as it ensures effective communication in a foreign language environment for solving professional, business, and academic tasks in an international context [1]. O. Zelikovska considers intercultural competence to be a significant factor in the professional training of future economists and proposes an authorial methodology for its formation, implemented in the process of foreign

language learning through three stages: the development of motivation for the parallel acquisition of language and culture, the acquisition of subject-professional and culture-specific knowledge, and the development of relevant skills and abilities [2]. The scientific and methodological foundations for forming foreign language competence among future economists in the process of integrated learning are examined by B. Cherniavskyi, who emphasizes a comprehensive approach to combining language and professional training [3].

At the same time, the problem of defining the content of instruction and substantiating effective approaches to the formation of foreign language speech competence of specialists in the field of international economic relations remains open and debatable. This is predetermined not only by the dynamic nature of socio-economic processes and the transformation of educational paradigms, but also by the continuous changes in professional requirements for international economists in the context of globalization and international economic interaction. Existing methodological approaches do not always fully meet contemporary challenges related to the integration of academic and professional communication, the development of intercultural sensitivity, and adaptation to the rapid renewal of the information and educational environment.

Moreover, the content of foreign language training and the didactic tools for its implementation require systematic reconsideration in light of emerging scientific concepts, improvements in the material and technical infrastructure of higher education, and the impact of contemporary socio-political factors, which have intensified in recent years at both national and global levels. Under these conditions, there is a growing need for a scientifically grounded determination of the means and methods for developing foreign language speech competence in future international economists within the course of foreign language of academic and professional communication.

The purpose of the article is to provide a theoretical substantiation and analysis of effective means for the formation of foreign language speech competence of future international economists in the context of academic and professional communication. To achieve this goal, the study sets out to address the following objectives: to clarify the essence of foreign language speech competence within the professional training of international economists; to analyse contemporary approaches to its formation; and to identify and substantiate effective didactic tools for the development of foreign language academic and professional speech competence under the conditions of the modern educational process.

To achieve the stated objective, the study employs a set of complementary methods of scientific inquiry. Theoretical methods include analysis (theoretical and comparative), generalization, systematization, and comparison of various scholarly approaches and perspectives on the problem under study, which made it possible to clarify the conceptual foundations of foreign language speech competence formation. Content analysis of regulatory and curricular documents was used to identify current requirements for foreign language training of specialists in the field of international economic relations. The modelling method was applied to determine the essence and structural components of foreign language speech competence. Among the empirical methods, observation was used, which allowed for identifying the level of foreign language speech competence formation in future specialists in international economic relations.

Results

The European academic and educational community has consistently sought to address the problem of unifying approaches to foreign language education in higher education institutions, driven by the growing academic and professional mobility and the need to ensure comparable learning outcomes. An important step in this direction was the adoption of the document *“Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment”* [4], which established the conceptual foundations of contemporary language

education. These recommendations are aimed at intensifying the processes of foreign language learning in order to enhance learners' mobility, expand access to information resources, and increase the effectiveness of international communication while preserving cultural diversity. In the context of training future economists specializing in international economic relations, the provisions of the Common European Framework acquire particular significance, as they orient the educational process toward the formation of foreign language speech competence as an integrative ability to effectively engage in academic and professional communication within an intercultural environment. The unification of goals, strategies, approaches, and requirements for language learning proposed by the Council of Europe creates a methodological basis for the development of curricula in foreign language academic and professional communication that correspond to the specific features of the future professional activity of international economists. The application of this document facilitates the coordination of the activities of teachers, education managers, and developers of educational and methodological support, and ensures the purposeful and systematic development of speech skills necessary for participation in international negotiations, analytical work, and professional business communication [4].

The Concept for the Development of Economic Education in Ukraine emphasizes that the strategic goal of university-level economic education is to train a comprehensively developed economics professional endowed with a broad scientific worldview, the ability for critical thinking, and the capacity for self-realization as an economically active member of society [5]. Under contemporary conditions of globalization and the intensification of international economic interaction, the achievement of this goal is inconceivable without a well-formed foreign language speech competence that ensures the effective participation of future international economists in academic and professional communication. Mastery of a foreign language of academic and professional communication is therefore regarded as a necessary prerequisite for graduates' integration into the international academic, educational, and professional space, their competitiveness in the global labour market, and their capacity for continuous professional development.

Professional training of future specialists in international economic relations constitutes an integral and multidimensional process aimed at developing a system of practical knowledge, professional skills and abilities, fostering sustained motivation for learning and cognitive activity, as well as the capacity for self-directed organization of the educational process and continuous professional self-improvement. In Ukraine, the requirements for the professional competence of specialists in international economic relations are defined in the relevant higher education standard, which outlines a set of general and professional competencies necessary for performing analytical, managerial, communicative, and foreign economic activities [6]. It should be emphasized that, in accordance with the requirements of state higher education standards at various educational levels, the foreign language competence of a future specialist in international economic relations is primarily defined by the ability to use a foreign language as an effective instrument of professional and personal development. This competence presupposes readiness for activity in the international economic environment, awareness of the value of cultural diversity and the principles of multiculturalism, as well as the development of intercultural interaction skills. An essential component of such competence is the ability to communicate fluently in a foreign language, both orally and in writing, when discussing the results of scientific research, innovative solutions, and professional issues. In addition, a future specialist is expected to possess the skills required for public business and academic communication, including presentations, negotiations, and professional discussions, as well as the ability to effectively address communicative tasks in the state language and foreign languages across various professional and academic contexts [7].

O. I. Kamenskyi interprets the English-language competence of future economists as an integrated professional capacity to effectively address specialized and educational tasks of an

economic nature through the use of the English language. The scholar emphasizes that this competence is formed through the functional unity of two interrelated components. The first component is English-language professional communicative competence, which encompasses organizational, pragmatic, and subject-related elements and ensures effective participation of future specialists in professional communication. The second component is information-cognitive competence, which includes communicative-cognitive and information-cognitive skills and abilities and is oriented toward the processing, interpretation, and application of professional information in English. Within this approach, English-language competence is viewed as a complex characteristic of the professional training of an economist, integrating linguistic, communicative, and cognitive resources and ensuring readiness for professional activity in the international economic environment [8]. In addition to the concept of foreign language competence, scholarly research widely employs other terms that are close or equivalent in their substantive meaning within the framework of this study, including “foreign language communicative competence,” “foreign language intercultural communicative competence,” “foreign language lexical competence,” and “professionally oriented communicative competence” [9].

According to current regulatory documents and scholarly research in the field of foreign language teaching methodology, the objectives of foreign language training are defined through the level of formation of key competences, in particular linguistic, sociocultural, and professional ones. For each field of study, typical speech situations are usually designed to reflect both everyday and professionally oriented communication. In the context of training specialists in international economic relations, this necessitates a comprehensive analysis of a number of parameters, namely: the set of competences and competencies specified in educational programmes; typical professional and everyday communicative situations; as well as the specific professional communicative needs of future international economists [10].

The findings derived from surveys of practicing professionals, as well as instructors and students involved in the professional training of international economists, are of considerable importance. At the same time, the interpretation of data obtained through the analysis of professional needs and the incorporation of these results into the design of course syllabi and the selection of teaching tools are characterized by both objective and subjective dimensions. This process is determined not only by diagnostic outcomes but also by the individual pedagogical experience and teaching style of a particular instructor. Professional training necessarily involves the maximum integration of professionally oriented topics and specialized terminology into the content of foreign language instruction. However, the teaching of a foreign language and foreign language speech has its own specific features, which manifest themselves in the formation of competencies and competences that can be fully developed only within the framework of this academic discipline [11].

Developing this idea further, it should be noted that contemporary foreign language teaching methodology includes approaches that envisage the full integration of foreign language instruction with subject-specific disciplines within the process of professional training. One such approach is CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), the essence of which lies in combining the acquisition of linguistic resources with the mastery of disciplinary content. Integrated language and content learning, or content-based instruction, has gained considerable popularity in the academic community in recent years. Unlike the traditional model, in which professional subject matter serves merely a supplementary or illustrative function within a foreign language course, the integrated approach aligns the language curriculum with subject-specific programmes in terms of content, organizational logic, and, in some cases, chronology. As a result, students acquire professional knowledge directly through the medium of a foreign language, while the development of foreign language skills and abilities takes place within clearly defined logical and temporal frameworks determined by the structure of the relevant academic disciplines [12]. The advantage of this

approach lies in the interdependent formation of professional and foreign language competences, which results in a synergistic effect. In particular, engaging with educational material and becoming familiar with concepts and phenomena simultaneously in the native and a foreign language may prove to be more effective and reliable than relying exclusively on the native language as the medium of instructional communication. At the same time, the practical implementation of an integrated approach is accompanied by a number of challenges, since foreign language instructors do not always possess sufficient subject-specific training or certification in core professional disciplines, just as subject-matter teachers, as a rule, are not specialized in foreign language teaching. As a result, integrated language-and-content instruction may lead to a fragmented nature of students' language training, given that under such conditions foreign language learning does not always follow a systematic trajectory, while grammatical, lexical, and phonetic phenomena often play only a supportive role in the process of mastering the content of professional disciplines [13].

A considerable body of scholarly research suggests that, in the process of teaching a foreign language (primarily English) to future specialists in international economic relations, the CLIL concept possesses significant didactic potential and can be effectively applied in instructional practice. This assumption is supported by the experience of higher education instructors who, alongside textbooks recommended for the relevant specialty, actively incorporate authentic professional textbooks, scholarly publications, and Internet-based materials, including audio and video resources, into the educational process. The advancement of information technologies has led to a gradual reduction in instructors' reliance on traditional textbooks and standardized teaching and learning packages. Under contemporary conditions, strict adherence to prescribed methodological guidelines is no longer considered sufficient to ensure the quality of foreign language training. Instead, instructors increasingly assume responsibility for the independent selection of relevant visual, textual, and audio-visual materials aimed at enhancing student motivation, diversifying types of speech activity, and intensifying professionally oriented foreign language practice. Moreover, foreign language instruction in higher education institutions is increasingly characterized by an orientation toward structuring course content in line with the requirements of international standardized language examinations [14]. Such an approach facilitates the integration of foreign language speech competence development with the formation of students' readiness to use a foreign language of academic and professional communication in the international educational and economic environment.

Specialists in the field of international economic relations, given the specific nature of their professional activity, must be capable of free and effective communication with foreign partners as well as with representatives of other professional communities, using both a foreign language of everyday communication and the specialized language of the relevant field. In this context, it is appropriate to highlight another significant characteristic of the content underlying the formation of foreign language speech competence in future international economists. This characteristic lies in the fact that the thematic scope of instruction, the corresponding lexical minimum, and the models of speech behaviour in professional situations simultaneously encompass the communicative domains of both economists and specialists in international relations. Consequently, the foreign language speech competence of future specialists in international economic relations, in its professional dimension, integrates elements of competencies inherent in both the economic and international political fields. Given that the training of an international economist involves mastering knowledge in international trade, international monetary and credit relations, enterprise economics, statistics, as well as the theory and history of international relations and diplomacy, it becomes evident that the development of educational programs is accompanied by a number of complex and non-standard tasks. These include determining an optimal thematic and speech minimum, selecting textbooks, teaching aids, and supplementary didactic materials, utilizing Internet resources,

and substantiating the structural organization of academic disciplines, content modules, and forms of learning outcomes assessment.

In the methodology of foreign language teaching, sociocultural competence is regarded as one of the key components of the process of forming foreign language speech competence, as explicitly articulated, in particular, in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages [4]. In the methodology of foreign language teaching, sociocultural competence is regarded as one of the key components of the process of forming foreign language speech competence, which is explicitly stated, *inter alia*, in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages.

Future specialists in the field of international economic relations are no exception in this regard. The acquisition of a foreign language is accompanied by students' familiarization with the cultural heritage of the countries whose language is being studied, as well as with so-called "realia" that are reflected both in general language use and in professionally oriented sublanguage. With respect to the English language, the sphere of international economic relations and English as a tool of international communication in this field should be considered in close interconnection. This assertion is relevant to both oral and written professional communication. Particular attention should be paid to English-language terminology in international economics, a significant proportion of which, as a result of active borrowing, functions in various languages, including Ukrainian, as internationalisms. At the same time, the process of mastering such vocabulary requires a high degree of accuracy and a critical approach on the part of both instructors and students when establishing semantic equivalence between English terms and their Ukrainian counterparts. In this context, the correct presentation of new lexical units in the educational process becomes especially important, taking into account both linguistic and sociocultural factors of their functioning within professional discourse.

Country studies competence of future specialists in international economic relations is closely interconnected with their professional training in accordance with the chosen field of specialization. In this context, an important task is to develop students' ability to work effectively with various information sources, including searching for, analysing, and interpreting data, particularly through the use of English and other foreign languages. Such skills constitute a necessary prerequisite for full-fledged professional activity in the field of international economic relations and ensure graduates' readiness to operate in a multilingual and information-intensive professional environment.

A significant potential for developing the competences envisaged by the educational programme for the training of future specialists in international economic relations is demonstrated by such types of learning activities as extensive reading of professionally oriented literature in a foreign language in accordance with established methodological guidelines and the completion of accompanying tasks, as well as the systematic use of authentic video and audio materials. Authentic texts addressing issues of international economics are valuable not only in terms of their informational content and the acquisition of professional terminology, but also from a linguistic perspective. They are characterized by specific stylistic features, reflect typical speech patterns of professional discourse, and contain models of professional communicative behaviour. In this regard, such materials can and should serve as objects of comprehensive analysis within the educational process, contributing to the development of students' foreign language speech competence in the context of foreign language academic and professional communication.

According to contemporary approaches to foreign language teaching, the core principle of which is the development of foreign language communication through direct communicative activity, translation from a foreign language into the native language or vice versa is not regarded as an independent instructional goal for students of non-linguistic specialties. Consequently, translation is either not used at all in the educational process or is applied only episodically as an auxiliary didactic tool. This approach can be considered justified to a certain

extent, as the successful implementation of communicative language teaching methodologies in various types of educational institutions, including higher education institutions, confirms its effectiveness. The majority of university instructors do not consider the systematic use of translation during practical foreign language classes to be necessary.

At the same time, in our view, the potential of translation in the process of forming professionally oriented foreign language competence remains underestimated. This is primarily due to the complexity of mastering specialized foreign language terminology, for which accurate and well-considered translation may serve as an effective means of achieving deeper and, most importantly, adequate comprehension of term meanings. In addition, particular importance is attached to adherence to the stylistic features of the foreign-language original (whether written or oral) and to the accurate identification of appropriate equivalents in the native language. In this context, the comparison of foreign-language and native-language samples contributes to a more accurate mastery of professional terminology and the stylistic features of speech in typical situations of professional communication in a foreign language. In addition, the use of translation indirectly creates conditions for improving students' professional discourse in their native language, which is also of considerable importance for achieving the objectives of professional training. Thus, when applied in a methodologically balanced manner, translation may be regarded not as an alternative to communicative language teaching, but as its functional complement in the process of forming foreign language speech competence of future specialists in international economic relations.

The analysis of the examined issues provides grounds to assert that the effectiveness of forming professional competencies in the process of studying a foreign language of academic and professional communication is largely determined by the creation of a set of necessary conditions. First, these include organizational conditions, which involve the rational structuring of the educational process aimed at the systematic enhancement of learners' professional competence. Second, methodological conditions encompass the identification of optimal forms and content of professionally oriented foreign language instruction, taking into account interdisciplinary links and the specific nature of future professional activity. Third, technological conditions include the application of effective assessment and evaluation procedures, the use of active and interactive learning formats, as well as appropriate technical support for the educational process. Fourth, psychological and pedagogical conditions consist in fostering stable positive motivation for learning, selecting instructional materials capable of activating students' cognitive, creative, and intellectual engagement, and stimulating their initiative and professional self-development.

In our view, a particularly important role in the process of foreign language training of future specialists in international economic relations within courses of foreign language for academic and professional communication is played by the integration of teaching methods based on different types of educational and professional activities. In particular, the presentation method creates conditions for students to demonstrate systematized professional knowledge and developed skills of foreign language communication. The problem-based learning method is aimed at activating students' exploratory and research activities, fostering in-depth professional knowledge, and developing independence in solving educational and professional tasks. The method of business games is also of considerable importance, as it allows for the simulation of typical and non-standard situations of future professional activity and international economic practice, the resolution of which requires the application of professional knowledge and practical skills of foreign language communication. Training exercises serve as an effective tool for mastering foreign language linguistic and speech resources, thereby contributing to the development of foreign language professional communication skills. The use of the case method, in turn, ensures not only the development of foreign language communicative competence but also the formation of critical thinking, as well

as the activation of group interaction and collaborative foreign language activity among students.

An important aspect of foreign language training is ensuring the coordinated interaction of different forms of organizing the educational process in the course of foreign language learning for academic and professional communication. This involves combining traditional approaches to the professional and language training of future specialists in higher education institutions with innovative models of instructional organization, in particular through the implementation of blended learning, which integrates online and offline formats of educational activity.

Conclusions

The findings of the study indicate that the effectiveness of professional activity of contemporary specialists in international economic relations is determined not only by a system of specialized economic knowledge but also by well-developed skills and abilities of foreign-language professional communication aimed at effective interaction with international business partners. In this context, foreign language proficiency functions as an essential instrument for academic and professional communication, enabling future international economists to participate fully in international economic discourse, professional cooperation, and intercultural interaction.

The study substantiates that foreign language instruction in higher education institutions should be oriented toward the formation of foreign-language communicative competence at the level of its practical application in professional contexts. The process of foreign-language training must be structured in accordance with the competence-based approach, which presupposes such an organization of instruction in foreign language academic and professional communication that ensures the integrated development of linguistic, sociocultural, and professional components of competence. The implementation of effective organizational, methodological, technological, and psychological-pedagogical conditions contributes to the formation of foreign-language speech competence, allowing future specialists to act effectively in both typical and non-standard professional situations, adapt to the dynamic requirements of the global economic environment, and engage in meaningful international dialogue.

Despite the theoretical and analytical value of the present study, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the research is predominantly theoretical in nature and is based on the analysis and synthesis of existing scholarly literature, normative documents, and methodological approaches. Although elements of empirical observation were employed, the study does not include large-scale experimental verification or quantitative assessment of learning outcomes, which may limit the generalizability of the findings across different institutional and educational contexts.

Second, the focus of the study is confined to the professional training of future specialists in international economic relations within higher education institutions. Consequently, the conclusions may not be fully transferable to students of other non-linguistic specializations or to alternative educational settings without appropriate adaptation. In addition, the implementation of certain didactic approaches discussed in the article – particularly integrated and blended learning models – may depend on institutional resources, instructors' methodological readiness, and students' prior language proficiency, which were not examined in detail in this research.

Future research perspectives are associated with the development, empirical validation, and practical implementation of a comprehensive model for forming foreign language speech competence of future international economists within the framework of foreign language of academic and professional communication. Particular attention should be paid to the application of blended learning technologies, including digital platforms, interactive tools, and online collaborative environments. Further studies may also focus on experimental testing of

specific instructional methods, comparative analysis of different pedagogical models, and assessment of their effectiveness in enhancing students' professional communicative performance in authentic international contexts.

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